
Ways to Determine the Possibilities of Increasing the Range of New Services Based on Swot Analysis of Hostel Hotels

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Abstract. *Today, in the conditions of high competition in the services market, the management of every organization prioritizes the task of maintaining and increasing its competitiveness.*

Keywords: *tourists, accommodation, guests, hotels, motels.*

INTRODUCTION

The field of tourism and special hospitality depends on external and internal factors that affect the activity of hotels and determine their development vector. The problem of strategic management of the placement company is undoubtedly relevant, because the need to find ways to develop new relationships with customers and suppliers, to develop new services that are not similar among competitors, etc., is increasing. In turn, each management decision should be balanced and provided with reliable, systematic information about the external and internal environment of the hotel organization. Today, several factors hinder the expansion of the range of services in hotels. Despite the fact that most of the placement facilities are non-state owned, the lack of a favorable investment environment for attracting local and foreign investments does not allow for the reconstruction of placement facilities.

Based on the SWOT analysis of deployment tools, it is possible to determine the possibilities of expanding new types of services. A unique feature of SWOT analysis is that it provides wide opportunities for interpretation. Due to the open, unstructured and flexible form of such analysis, it allows combining its results with other management ideas. Conducting a SWOT analysis for the Gul zamin Saykal hostel begins with an assessment of the company's actual strategic position, which shows the company's current strategy in harmony with its internal resources and market opportunities. For this, it is necessary to group the strengths and weaknesses of the hostel into separate elements of the SWOT matrix. Based on the main factors of success, the strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the hostel are described, the ratio of these elements in the SWOT matrix helps to form the priorities of strategic development.

The efficiency of hostels is characterized by the following indicators: the number of rooms, the payment ratio of the room fund, the class of service, the set of additional services. The seasonality of the bedroom is calculated using the coefficient of payment. Before analyzing business indicators in deployment tools, it is necessary to understand at what stage the enterprise is. Placement companies are increasingly looking for new opportunities in the formation of their product strategy, and are attracting opportunities from the newest and most profitable sectors, especially the SPA industry.

The results show how the hostel can do better. It is desirable to minimize the need to use one's strengths to realize opportunities and to minimize the weaknesses and risks or avoid them. The analysis shows that the strengths of the hostel are sufficient, which means that this placement tool will be able to sufficiently increase the range of services and receive customers based on the number pool. When conducting research among hostel customers, it was found that 60% of them are women and the remaining 40% are men. As the results of the analysis show, taking into account that the main customers are women, it would be appropriate if the range of additional services, such as beauty salons and entertainment programs, were increased in the hostel.

As a result of a customer survey conducted on the basis of marketing research, customers said that there should be gyms inside the hostels, there should be children's playgrounds in the hostel area, and most of the customers said that there should be a swimming pool around this accommodation facility.

Figure 3.3.2. Gender of customers visiting the hostel is in %

There are several advantages of accepting customers by increasing the range of services in placement tools:

Cheap prices: Renting a hostel is cheaper than renting an entire room or a hotel room. In addition, hostels often allow you to save money on restaurants and cafes. Guests have the opportunity to cook in the shared kitchen.

The opportunity to make new friends, hostels are visited by people who like to communicate more and are open to new acquaintances. Thus, it is easy to chat with other guests or organize a game with a roommate in the common living area. Here, customers can contact the hostel administrator for city tours or route advice.

Increasing the range of services in placement tools is an effective way to fight competition. This is another source of profit and a way to improve service quality. The current offer of additional services allows to have a positive impact on the business image.

If there is space in the accommodation vehicle, it can be used for various banquets and animation events. This service significantly expands the target audience of a hotel or other accommodation facility. For example, if a restaurant is rented for a party, the residents of the city will most likely become its regular customers.

Vending machines, souvenir shops, and tourism information centers can be installed in the entrance lobby to accommodation facilities. Thus, the client can find all the information inside the deployment tool, and this will definitely have a positive effect on the quality of service.

Positive cooperation with taxi services and travel companies. Room service is especially popular in accommodation facilities such as hostels where meals are not provided.

Cooperation with tourist agencies ensures an additional flow of tourists and tour groups to fully fill the hotel during the season. The creation of tourist information centers in small accommodation facilities such as hostels is also very effective.

Organization of a bar, restaurant, billiard club and animation events based on them will provide an additional flow of visitors at the expense of city residents. Only these halls should be located outside the hotel building.

Cooperation with corporate clients is also an additional service that significantly increases profits. Enterprise customers ensure that the deployment tool is busy at low times. Their main requirement is to place everything necessary for holding corporate events in one hotel: halls for training and conferences, minimum office equipment for work, banquet hall and transfer.

Organization of forums and trainings. It can be as simple as renting a conference room, as well as arranging accommodation and leisure for event guests. As part of such events, it is possible to accommodate foreign guests from different cities.

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